

A NOTE ON THE NEW FORMULA FOR CHAKSINE.

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In a recent paper by Kapur, Gaiind, Narang and Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 281) a new formula $C_{11}H_{21}O_3N_3$ has been given to chaksine as against $C_{12}H_{21}O_2N_3$ tentatively assigned by us to the two isomeric bases chaksine and *i*-ochaksine, isolated as bicarbonate and carbonate respectively, from the seeds of *Cassia absus*, Linn. (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 2A, 421). Ray *et al* state that they undertook this work, as the iodine content of the iodide noted by us was much too low,* and we had moreover relied on the analysis of chaksine bicarbonate "which was supposed to have the composition $C_{12}H_{20}ON_3 \cdot HCO_3, \frac{1}{2}H_2O$." They further state: "it was dehydrated by heating at 100° and the anhydrous substance analysed. There is grave objection to accept the loss in *vacuo* at 100° to be due to the loss of $\frac{1}{2}H_2O$. It is quite well known that the bicarbonates of organic bases, like those of an alkali metal, lose carbon dioxide on heating as indeed has been found to be the case by us."

It would appear from the above reference that the formula for the chaksine bicarbonate, $C_{12}H_{20}ON_3 \cdot HCO_3, \frac{1}{2}H_2O$, was derived by us only on the basis of an analysis of the anhydrous substance. This, however, is contrary to the facts. As would be seen from a reference to the original paper, the C, H and N values of the air-dried bicarbonate as well as of the anhydrous product were determined. Moreover, the loss of weight on drying at 100° in *vacuo* to constant weight was recorded and found to correspond to the required $\frac{1}{2}H_2O$. As regards the general behaviour of the carbonates or bicarbonates of the bases towards heat, pointed out by Ray *et al*, it would be well to recognise the large range of stability of the carbonates of organic bases, which principally varies with the strength of the basic radical but may also be due to other indeterminate factors. There are carbonates which decompose on heating in low boiling organic solvents while others are stable well above 200° . A parallel to the heat resistance of carbonates is the stability of certain hydrates. Generally speaking water of crystallisation is removed at 100° in *vacuo* but organic compounds are known which are completely dehydrated only at temperatures approaching 200° .

* Ray and collaborators' reference to our iodine value as 39.4 is apparently a misprint. The iodine content noted by us was 34.9 as against 36.39% calculated. This discrepancy in the iodine value of a quaternary iodide, dried at 100° in *vacuo*, had its obvious explanation.

However, considering the grounds on which Ray and co-workers undertook their work on chaksine, it would have been rational to expect an actual repetition of our work. This has been inexplicably avoided. Neither the carbonate nor the chloroplatinate have been analysed and the iodine content of the iodide has not been checked. On the contrary they have supported their C, H, and N values of the iodide with the iodine content noted by us. In this connection it is also striking that they have given the analytical data for C, H and N of the chloride and bromide but have avoided any reference to halogen values of these salts. As to the analytical data of the salts on which Ray *et al* have based their new formula for chaksine, it has further got to be noted that, except for the sulphate which melts at 317° and is highly incombustible, none of the other salts are noted by them to have been dried in *vacuo* to constant weight before analysis. Neglect of careful dehydration of the salts may have been partly responsible for their low carbon values.

In regard to the melting point of the iodide Ray and co-workers note 180° after drying in high *vacuo* at 100° , as against 168° (decomp.) recorded by us after drying at ordinary temperature in *vacuo*. A parallel observation of the melting points after drying under the same conditions would have been desirable, and it is surprising that they make no reference to it, as a quantity of the iodide was actually sent by one of us (S. S.) to the senior author at his own request.

In conclusion, it is obvious that the analysis of carbonates is not the best method of arriving at the formula of a base. As, however, the analysis of the pure base was excluded owing to the avidity with which chaksine and isochaksine absorb carbon dioxide from the atmosphere, and the undependability of carbon values in highly incombustible salts of alkaloids is a fact of common experience, a complete analysis of the chloroplatinate along with that of the carbonate, before and after drying at 100° , had to be admitted by us as a fair basis for a working molecular formula of chaksine and its isomer. Systematic investigation of the constitution of the two bases may eventually establish this formula or necessitate slight alterations. Work with this object is being carried out by us and the results will be communicated in due course.

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